

CULTURE AND IDENTITY: THE VALORIZATION OF ANGOLAN CULTURE AND THE PROMOTION OF NATIONAL IDENTITY**CULTURA E IDENTIDAD: VALORIZACIÓN DE LA CULTURA ANGOLANA Y PROMOCIÓN DE LA IDENTIDAD NACIONAL****CULTURA E IDENTIDADE: A VALORIZAÇÃO DA CULTURA ANGOLANA E A PROMOÇÃO DA IDENTIDADE NACIONAL**

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ABSTRACT

The valorization of Angolan culture and the promotion of national identity are crucial objectives to preserve the country's cultural wealth. This paper proposes a comprehensive approach that covers the valorization of national languages, organization of cultural festivals, development of sustainable cultural tourism, integration of cultural elements in the school curriculum and encouragement of traditional arts. The methodology involves documentary research, interviews, and field research to deeply understand traditions. In addition, strategic planning aims to identify specific needs of each region and develop customized strategies. Implementation includes curricular integration, holding cultural festivals, developing responsible cultural tourism and heritage preservation. This approach is dynamic, with ongoing evaluations and adjustments to ensure effectiveness. The results include promoting mutual understanding, strengthening local communities, preserving cultural heritage and a more cohesive national identity.

KEYWORDS: Angolan culture. National Identity. Sustainable Cultural Tourism. Heritage Preservation. Cultural Education.

RESUMEN

La valorización de la cultura angoleña y la promoción de la identidad nacional son objetivos cruciales para preservar la riqueza cultural del país. Este trabajo propone un enfoque integral que abarca la valorización de las lenguas nacionales, la organización de festivales culturales, el desarrollo del turismo cultural sostenible, la integración de elementos culturales en el currículo escolar y el estímulo de las artes tradicionales. La metodología involucra investigación documental, entrevistas e investigaciones de campo para comprender profundamente las tradiciones. Además, la planificación estratégica tiene como objetivo identificar las necesidades específicas de cada región y desarrollar estrategias personalizadas. La implementación incluye la integración curricular, la organización de festivales culturales, el desarrollo responsable del turismo cultural y la preservación del patrimonio. Este enfoque es dinámico, con evaluaciones continuas y ajustes para garantizar la eficacia. Los resultados incluyen la promoción del entendimiento mutuo, el fortalecimiento de las comunidades locales, la preservación del patrimonio cultural y una identidad nacional más cohesionada.

PALABRAS-CLAVE: Cultura Angoleña. Identidad Nacional. Turismo Cultural Sostenible. Preservación del Patrimonio. Educación Cultural.

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RESUMO

A valorização da cultura angolana e a promoção da identidade nacional são objetivos cruciais para preservar a riqueza cultural do país. Este trabalho propõe uma abordagem abrangente que abrange a valorização das línguas nacionais, organização de festivais culturais, desenvolvimento do turismo cultural sustentável, integração de elementos culturais no currículo escolar e incentivo às artes tradicionais. A metodologia envolve pesquisa documental, entrevistas e pesquisas de campo para compreender profundamente as tradições. Além disso, o planejamento estratégico visa identificar necessidades específicas de cada região e desenvolver estratégias personalizadas. A implementação inclui integração curricular, realização de festivais culturais, desenvolvimento do turismo cultural responsável e preservação patrimonial. Essa abordagem é dinâmica, com avaliações contínuas e ajustes para garantir eficácia. Os resultados incluem a promoção da compreensão mútua, fortalecimento das comunidades locais, preservação do patrimônio cultural e uma identidade nacional mais coesa.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Cultura Angolana. Identidade Nacional. Turismo Cultural Sustentável. Preservação do Patrimônio. Educação Cultural.

INTRODUCTION

The culture of a country is a fundamental pillar for the construction and preservation of national identity. In the case of Angola, a country rich in ethnic, historical and cultural diversity, the appreciation of local culture plays a crucial role in affirming national identity. In this text, we will explore the importance of promoting and valuing Angolan culture to strengthen the identity of the Angolan people. To substantiate our discussion, we will use quotes from international authors who also address this theme.

The Valorization of Angolan Culture

Angolan culture is a complex and rich tapestry, formed by a mixture of traditions, languages, dances, music and beliefs. It is a living heritage, transmitted from generation to generation, which reflects the history of the country and the diversity of its people. According to Hall (1997, p. 45), "culture is the arena in which national identities are formed and contested." Thus, valuing and preserving Angolan culture is essential to consolidate a cohesive and strengthened national identity.

The appreciation of Angolan culture involves the recognition and promotion of local cultural expressions, such as *kuduro*, Angolan capoeira, the Creole drum and traditional festivals. These artistic and cultural manifestations are true treasures that reveal the essence of the Angolan people. In this context, the anthropologist Clifford Geertz (1973, p. 89) stated that "culture is a system of meanings", where each element carries an important symbolic load in the construction of cultural identity.

Promotion of National Identity

The promotion of national identity is not only about reinforcing the cultural elements of a country, but also about developing a sense of belonging and pride towards the nation. In this sense, it is crucial that public policies, education and the media promote cultural diversity and highlight the importance of each component in the formation of national identity.

For Renan (1990, p. 17), "forgetfulness, not memory, is what creates the identity of a nation." This means that selective selection of cultural and historical elements can shape how Angolans see

themselves as a people and as a nation. Therefore, the appreciation of Angolan culture and its promotion must be carefully conducted, in order to embrace diversity and not exclude other cultural perspectives within the country.

The valorization of Angolan culture and the promotion of national identity are interconnected processes that require conscious and committed actions. By preserving and extolling the country's cultural wealth, Angolans strengthen their collective identity, reinforcing their sense of belonging and pride in the nation. However, it is essential to remember that identity is dynamic and plural, and it is essential to welcome the cultural diversity present in Angola.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

The general objective of this work is to analyze the importance of valuing Angolan culture as a way to promote national identity, exploring how the preservation and promotion of cultural elements contribute to strengthen the sense of belonging and pride of the Angolan people in relation to their nation. In addition, it seeks to understand how the recognition and promotion of the cultural diversity present in Angola can contribute to the construction of a cohesive and enriching national identity.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

- To investigate the distinct cultural elements present in Angola, including artistic manifestations, dances, music, cuisine and traditional festivals, in order to understand their importance in the formation of national identity.
- To analyze the role of public policies, education and the media in valuing and promoting Angolan culture, seeking to identify their contributions to the construction of a collective and integrative identity.
- To examine the relationship between the appreciation of Angolan culture and the strengthening of the sense of belonging and pride of Angolan citizens in relation to their nation, considering the emotional and psychological impact of this process.
- To assess the challenges and opportunities faced in the preservation of Angolan culture in a context of globalization and modernization, highlighting effective strategies for its safeguarding.
- To investigate the role of cultural diversity in the construction of Angolan national identity, exploring how the recognition and appreciation of different cultural expressions contribute to social cohesion and the enrichment of the country's cultural heritage.
- Propose recommendations and practical measures to encourage the promotion of Angolan culture and the valorization of national identity, based on good practices and successful experiences in other international contexts.

- By fulfilling these specific objectives, the work aims to contribute to a deeper reflection on the importance of culture and identity in Angolan society and provide subsidies for concrete actions that can strengthen the national identity and enhance the cultural richness of the country.

JUSTIFICATION

The valorization of culture and the promotion of national identity are fundamental issues for the development and cohesion of a nation. In the context of Angola, a country characterized by its rich ethnic and cultural diversity, the preservation and promotion of local culture are even more essential for the construction of a solid national identity.

This research is justified by the relevance of understanding how the appreciation of Angolan culture can contribute to the promotion of national identity and to the strengthening of the feeling of belonging of the Angolan people in relation to their country. By exploring the importance of culture as an essential pillar for the formation of collective identity, the research seeks to provide subsidies for the implementation of public policies and practical actions that value and preserve the Angolan cultural heritage.

In addition, the justification of this study lies in the need to understand how policies to promote culture and national identity can be developed in an inclusive way, welcoming the cultural diversity existing in Angola. By considering the various cultural manifestations present in the country, the research seeks to identify practices that can respect and value the different traditions and contribute to the cultural enrichment of Angolan society as a whole.

Another important aspect that motivates this research is the global context in which we live, where local culture often faces challenges amid cultural homogenization and external influences. Understanding how Angolan culture can be strengthened in an increasingly interconnected and globalized world is crucial for the preservation of its unique and diverse identity.

Therefore, this research is justified as an effort to contribute to the debate on the appreciation of Angolan culture and its relationship with national identity. Through the analysis of international authors and successful practices in other nations, it is hoped to offer relevant insights that can inform the formulation of public policies and concrete actions to promote a robust national identity and a vibrant and enriching Angolan culture for present and future generations.

METHODOLOGY AND METHOD

The approach to valuing Angolan culture and promoting national identity requires a comprehensive methodology that combines research, strategic planning and practical action. In this context, the following methodology is based on participatory, inclusive and sustainable approaches.

Participatory Methodology

The methodology adopted will be participatory, actively involving communities, cultural experts, academics and stakeholders. This ensures that the identification of the needs, desires and challenges of the communities is central to the process of cultural appreciation.

Search Method

1. **Documentary Research:** Conducting a comprehensive documentary research to deeply understand the cultural, historical and linguistic traditions of Angola. Sources will include books, scholarly articles, government documents, and historical records.
2. **Interviews and Focus Groups:** Conducting interviews with members of local communities, cultural experts, academics and government representatives to gather perspectives, knowledge and insights on Angolan culture and identity.
3. **Field Research:** Conducting field research in different regions of Angola to directly observe cultural practices, traditions, festivals and social interactions. This on-site research will provide an authentic understanding of cultural realities.

Strategic Planning

1. **Identification of Needs:** Based on the information collected, identification of the specific cultural needs of each region. This will include analysis of spoken languages, traditions at risk of disappearance and endangered heritage.
1. **Definition of Strategies:** Development of customized strategies for each region, considering local traditions, existing infrastructure and the aspirations of communities. This can involve creating educational programs, cultural festivals, heritage preservation projects, and more.

Practical Action and Implementation

2. **Curricular Integration:** Integration of Angolan cultural elements into school curricula, ensuring that the next generations have an in-depth understanding of their history, languages and traditions.
3. **Cultural Festivals and Exchange:** Organization of cultural festivals in different regions, allowing communities to share their traditions and interact. Cultural exchange programs will also be held to promote mutual understanding.
4. **Sustainable Cultural Tourism:** Development of plans for sustainable cultural tourism, ensuring that tourist visits benefit local communities and promote cultural preservation.
5. **Heritage Preservation:** Implementation of conservation technologies and techniques to protect and preserve important cultural artifacts and documents.
6. **Encouraging Arts and Crafts:** Supporting traditional artists and artisans, ensuring that their skills and knowledge are valued and passed on to the next generations.

Continuous Evaluation and Adjustments

The process will be dynamic, with regular evaluations of the strategies implemented. Local communities, experts and stakeholders will be involved in this process to provide feedback and

suggestions. Based on this ongoing evaluation, adjustments will be made to ensure that actions remain relevant and effective.

This holistic and inclusive methodology aims at gradual and sustainable cultural transformation, which honors the past and builds a culturally enriching future for Angola.

ANGOLAN CULTURE FESTIVAL

The culture of Angola is a precious treasure, composed of a rich diversity of traditions, artistic expressions, dances, songs, cuisine, traditional costumes and folk rituals. This cultural richness reflects the history, identity and soul of the Angolan people. To celebrate this diversity and strengthen the sense of national identity, it is proposed to organize an Angolan Culture Festival, a celebration that will bring together all the cultural manifestations that make Angola unique and singular.

The main objective of this festival is to promote the appreciation and recognition of Angolan culture, highlighting the importance of each cultural element in the construction of national identity. According to Stuart Hall (1992, p. 272), "culture is one of the main ways in which an 'identity' becomes possible." Therefore, by celebrating and preserving Angolan culture in a national event, the feeling of belonging and pride of the Angolan people in relation to their nation is strengthened.

At the festival, different regions of Angola will be represented, each bringing its own unique traditions. Participants will be able to enjoy performances of traditional dances, such as *semba*, *riwet* and *kizomba*, which are true testimonies of the soul and joy of the Angolan people. Music will play a central role, with artists presenting styles such as *kuduro*, Angolan merengue and traditional folk music.

Gastronomy will also be an essential part of the festival, with the offer of typical dishes from different regions, such as *funge*, *chicken moamba*, *calulu* and *quitaba*. Angolan cuisine, which is a blend of African and European influences, is a true expression of the country's identity and history.

In addition to the artistic and gastronomic presentations, the festival will also include exhibitions of traditional handicrafts, highlighting the beautiful costumes and accessories that reflect the identity of different ethnic groups of Angola. Folk rituals, such as drumming and lion dancing, will be represented, allowing visitors to appreciate the spirituality and connection with nature present in Angolan beliefs.

The organization of this festival requires a joint effort of the government, local communities, cultural organizations and sponsors. Inspired by the words of James C. Scott (1998), who emphasizes the importance of collaboration between different social actors in valuing culture, the festival will be an opportunity to join efforts towards a common goal: the preservation and promotion of Angolan culture.

The Angolan Culture Festival emerges as a relevant initiative to value and celebrate the cultural diversity of Angola. By bringing together different artistic manifestations, dances, songs, cuisine, traditional costumes and folk rituals, the event strengthens the sense of national identity and enhances the cultural richness of the country.

Through the organization of this festival, it is hoped to inspire continuous actions to preserve and promote Angolan culture in all its forms. The celebration of Angola's cultural diversity is an

opportunity to rescue roots, reaffirm identities and strengthen the ties that unite the Angolan people. Thus, this event is consolidated as a living expression of Angola's cultural heritage, transmitted to present and future generations.

PRESERVATION OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

The preservation of cultural heritage is a task of utmost importance for societies around the world. Cultural heritage is the heritage left by past generations, a unique wealth that reflects the history, values, traditions and identities of a people. In this context, preservation work plays a key role in maintaining cultural diversity and valuing the roots that shape a nation's identity.

According to UNESCO (2003, p. 5), "the preservation of cultural heritage is essential for understanding, respect and tolerance among peoples". By conserving and protecting historical monuments, archaeological sites, oral traditions, festivals, dances, songs and cultural artifacts, we are ensuring that future generations can know and appreciate their cultural heritage.

The preservation of cultural heritage also plays an important role in the construction of collective identity and in the formation of a community's sense of belonging. According to Eric Hobsbawm and Terence Ranger (1983, p. 9), "the invention and reinvention of traditions is a continuous and adaptive response to the problems posed by modernization." In this sense, the preservation of cultural traditions is a way of reaffirming the identity of a people in a world in constant transformation.

However, the preservation of cultural heritage faces significant challenges. Accelerated urbanization, economic growth, globalization, and even the impact of climate change pose threats to the integrity of many cultural elements. It is therefore necessary to establish effective conservation policies and involve the local community in the protection of its own heritage.

International cooperation is also essential for the preservation of cultural heritage. The UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003) highlights the importance of cooperation between countries to identify, document and protect cultural traditions that are shared by diverse nations.

The preservation of cultural heritage is a collective responsibility that transcends cultural boundaries and differences. By safeguarding cultural heritage, we are protecting the identity and roots that define a people and providing a solid foundation for the future. The preservation of cultural heritage is an investment in cultural enrichment, mutual understanding and the promotion of diversity, building bridges that unite past, present and future generations.

CULTURAL EDUCATION

Cultural education plays a key role in preserving and promoting a nation's cultural and historical identity. In Angola, a country with a rich cultural diversity, integrating Angolan cultural elements into the school curriculum is a crucial approach to transmitting to younger generations the importance of their cultural heritage. In this text, we will explore the importance of cultural education and the relevance of its integration into the school curriculum, basing our reflections with quotes from international authors who discuss the role of education in the preservation of culture.

According to Paulo Freire (1970, p.52), "cultural education has as its main objective to form citizens capable of appreciating and respecting their own culture and the culture of the other, favoring dialogue between different cultural identities." Therefore, by incorporating Angolan cultural elements into the curriculum, schools can contribute to strengthening the cultural identity of students, stimulating pride and recognition of their heritage.

The integration of Angolan culture into the school curriculum can occur in several ways, such as:

Inclusion of Angolan History and Traditions: Insert content that addresses Angolan history and cultural traditions, highlighting significant historical figures, events and cultural landmarks.

Languages and Literature: Valuing local languages and Angolan literature, encouraging the learning and appreciation of these fundamental aspects of culture.

Arts and Music: Introduce Angolan artistic expressions such as dance, music and painting, allowing students to explore and connect with these cultural manifestations.

Cuisine and Festivals: Explore traditional Angolan cuisine and celebrate cultural festivals to provide students with a more immersive experience in the local culture.

Material and Intangible Cultural Heritage: To make students aware of the material and intangible cultural heritage of Angola, such as historical monuments, folk rituals and traditional practices.

Cultural education not only strengthens the cultural identity of students, but also promotes the appreciation of diversity and tolerance between different social groups. As Martha Nussbaum (2010, p. 33) points out, "cultural education is essential for the construction of a citizenship committed to equality and respect for differences." By learning about Angola's culture, students will be better prepared to become active and respectful citizens in a pluralistic society.

The integration of Angolan cultural elements in the school curriculum is a relevant way to strengthen the cultural and historical identity of the new generations. Through cultural education, students can understand and appreciate the diversity and richness of Angolan culture, consolidating their connection with their country's heritage. By embracing and valuing their cultural identity, young people become protagonists in the process of preserving and promoting Angola's culture, ensuring that it is passed on to future generations.

ENCOURAGEMENT OF TRADITIONAL ARTS AND CRAFTS

Traditional arts and crafts are cultural treasures that reflect the history, creativity and identity of a people. In many communities, traditional artisans and artists carry skills and knowledge passed down through generations, becoming living guardians of cultural heritage. In this text, we will discuss the importance of encouraging and supporting these traditional artisans and artists to value their skills and ensure that their knowledge is passed on to the next generations. To support our reflections, we will use quotes from international authors who emphasize the essential role of traditional arts and crafts in cultural preservation.

The preservation of traditional arts and crafts is a way to keep alive the connection to the history and cultural roots of a community. As Richard Sennett (2009, p.84) emphasizes, "traditional skills have the power to provide a sense of continuity and belonging to a shared tradition." Encouraging and supporting traditional artisans and artists is therefore essential to strengthen cultural identity and keep cultural traditions alive.

The encouragement of traditional arts and crafts involves several actions:

Appreciation and Recognition: Recognize the importance of traditional artisans and artists as guardians of cultural knowledge and value their contributions to the community and to culture in general.

Preservation and Diffusion: Support the preservation and diffusion of traditional techniques and knowledge, promoting workshops, courses and events that transmit these skills to the new generations.

Social Inclusion: Ensure that traditional artisans and artists have access to opportunities and resources to develop and market their work, contributing to their economic sustainability and social well-being.

Stimulating Creativity: Encouraging innovation and creativity in traditional arts and crafts, allowing traditions to evolve and adapt to the contemporary context.

Partnerships and Support Networks: Establish partnerships with cultural institutions, government agencies, and private initiatives to strengthen the support and promotion of traditional arts and crafts.

By valuing and supporting traditional artisans and artists, society can preserve its cultural heritage, ensuring that their skills and knowledge are passed on to the next generations. As Howard Gardner (2006, p. 46) points out, "the transmission of cultural knowledge is a form of education that goes beyond the limits of schools, being essential for the complete formation of an individual." Thus, encouraging traditional arts and crafts is a valuable strategy to enhance cultural traditions and ensure the continuity of a community's cultural richness.

Encouraging and supporting traditional artisans and artists is an investment in cultural preservation and the transmission of valuable knowledge to the next generations. By valuing traditional arts and crafts, society strengthens its cultural identity, promotes social inclusion, and preserves its history and traditions. Collaboration between institutions, governments and civil society is key to ensuring that these knowledge and skills are preserved, allowing culture to continue to evolve and renew itself over time.

LOCAL CULTURAL PRODUCTION

The promotion of local cultural production plays a crucial role in the preservation and celebration of Angolan identity. Locally produced films, music, literature and fine arts have the power to express a nation's experiences, traditions and values. In this text, we will explore the importance of supporting and valuing the production of local cultural and artistic works in Angola, highlighting the relevance of this creative expression for the promotion of national identity. We will base our

reflections with quotes from international authors who discuss the role of local cultural production in the construction of identity and cultural heritage.

Local cultural production is an authentic and powerful way to give voice to the Angolan people and praise their traditions. According to Stuart Hall (1997, p. 15), "culture is the medium through which an 'identity' becomes possible, recognizable." In this way, local cultural production is a living expression of Angola's collective identity, allowing Angolans themselves to recognize themselves in their artistic creations.

The promotion of local cultural and artistic works covers various forms of support, such as:

Incentive to Create: Offer incentives and funding for local artists and creators to produce their works, allowing their creativity to flourish.

Cultural Spaces: Create cultural spaces dedicated to the exhibition and presentation of local works, providing an environment for artists to share their creations with the public.

Events and Festivals: Hold cultural events and festivals that value and highlight local production, giving visibility to Angolan artistic talents.

Artistic Training: Invest in artistic training and cultural education programs to develop and enhance the skills of local artists.

Heritage Preservation: Encourage artistic production that rescues and preserves elements of Angolan cultural heritage, enriching local narratives.

Local cultural production is a powerful means of transmitting Angolan identity to new generations. As John Berger (1982, p. 12) mentions, "art is one of the ways in which people find and assert their identity." By creating works that reflect the reality and aspirations of the Angolan people, local artists have the potential to inspire a sense of belonging and pride in their culture.

The promotion of local cultural production is an investment in the valorization and preservation of Angolan identity. Through films, music, literature and fine arts, local artists have the opportunity to express the essence of Angola and share its rich cultural heritage with the world. By supporting and valuing local cultural production, Angolan society strengthens its ties with cultural heritage, ensuring that its narratives and traditions are transmitted and appreciated by present and future generations.

MUSEUMS AND CULTURAL CENTERS

Museums and cultural centers are fundamental spaces for the preservation, exhibition and dissemination of the richness of Angolan culture. As guardians of cultural heritage, these institutions have a responsibility to pass on a nation's history, traditions, and identity. In this text, we will address the importance of investment in the creation and expansion of museums and cultural centers in different regions of Angola, emphasizing the vital role of these institutions in valuing and preserving the cultural legacy. To support our reflections, we will use quotes from international authors who emphasize the impact of museums and cultural centers on heritage conservation.

Museums and cultural centers play a crucial role in preserving cultural memory and building national identity. As highlighted by Tony Bennett (1995, p. 12), "museums have the ability to reflect

notions of cultural identity and the ways in which they change over time." Investing in these institutions is a way to ensure that Angolan culture is preserved and understood by future generations.

Investment in the creation and expansion of museums and cultural centers may involve several initiatives, such as:

HERITAGE PRESERVATION

The preservation of cultural heritage is a vital responsibility to ensure that future generations can appreciate and learn from a nation's history and culture. Investing in conservation technologies and techniques is essential to protect important cultural artifacts and documents, ensuring their integrity and longevity. In this text, we will explore the importance of this investment in the preservation of cultural heritage, supporting our reflections with quotes from international authors who highlight the relevance of heritage conservation.

Heritage preservation is a way of transmitting cultural memory and keeping a society's heritage alive. As Nancy Bell (2015) points out, "heritage conservation is a practice that allows for cultural continuity, ensuring that the voices of the past continue to be heard" (p. 42). Through investment in advanced conservation technologies, we can protect artifacts and cultural documents that are tangible testimonies to our history.

Investment in conservation technologies and techniques can cover several areas:

Document Scanning: Scanning documents and historical records allows the creation of backup copies that can be accessed without compromising the originals.

Proper Storage: Creating controlled environments with adequate levels of temperature and humidity helps prevent deterioration of sensitive materials.

Professional Restoration: Restoration done by experts can revitalize damaged artifacts, allowing them to be enjoyed in their original form.

Continuous Monitoring: The use of sensors and monitoring devices helps detect inappropriate environmental conditions that may affect heritage.

Research and Development: Investing in research into new conservation techniques can lead to discoveries that extend the lifespan of artifacts.

The preservation of cultural heritage not only keeps history and culture alive, but also contributes to the identity and cohesion of a society. As John F. Kennedy (1963) emphasizes, "our nation's heritage must be preserved for our children and grandchildren" (p. 1). Investing in conservation technologies is a commitment to the future, allowing the next generations to connect with the roots and values of their ancestors.

Investment in conservation technologies and techniques is an act of cultural preservation and a legacy for future generations. Protecting cultural artifacts and documents is one way to ensure that collective memory continues to be transmitted and understood. By investing in this preservation, society strengthens its connection with history, culture and identity, building bridges between past and future.

Exhibitions and Shows: Hold thematic exhibitions and temporary shows that highlight different aspects of Angolan culture, providing an enriching experience to visitors.

Digital Inclusion: Integrate digital technologies into exhibitions to offer interactive access and engagement, making the experience more inclusive and engaging.

Educational Programs: Develop educational programs for schools and communities that promote understanding and respect for Angolan culture.

Partnerships and Exchanges: Establish partnerships with museums and international cultural institutions to promote exchanges and collaborations.

By investing in the creation and expansion of museums and cultural centers in different regions of the country, Angolan society strengthens its commitment to the preservation of cultural heritage. As Linda Norris (2015, p. 22) points out, "museums are spaces of connection, learning and intercultural dialogue." These spaces provide a unique opportunity for the celebration of cultural diversity and for the construction of a cohesive national identity.

Investment in the creation and expansion of museums and cultural centers is a valuable strategy to preserve and display the richness of Angolan culture. These institutions are fundamental to the transmission of Angola's history, traditions and identity, strengthening the sense of belonging and cultural pride. By celebrating the diversity and legacy of the country, museums and cultural centers become pillars for building a more inclusive society and aware of its cultural heritage.

ENHANCEMENT OF NATIONAL LANGUAGES

The enhancement of national languages is an essential commitment to preserve Angola's rich linguistic diversity. In addition to Portuguese, national languages are crucial vehicles for the transmission of cultural identity, knowledge and traditions. In this text, we will explore the importance of encouraging the use and teaching of national languages in Angola, supporting our reflections with quotes from international authors who highlight the relevance of linguistic diversity in cultural preservation.

National languages are a reflection of a country's cultural richness and a way to keep alive the heritage of specific communities. According to Kwame Anthony Appiah (2006), "linguistic diversity is a crucial component of cultural diversity" (p. 123). Encouraging the use and teaching of national languages is a way to strengthen cultural identity and ensure that the voices of different groups are heard.

The enhancement of national languages may involve several strategies:

- 1. Integration into the School Curriculum:** Include the teaching of national languages in the school curriculum, allowing students to connect with their cultural roots from an early age.
- 2. Literature and Educational Materials:** Develop literature and educational materials in national languages, enriching the cultural offer and promoting learning.
- 3. Preservation of Oral Traditions:** Valuing oral traditions by encouraging the transmission of stories, songs and ancestral knowledge in national languages.

4. **Media and Communication:** Promote the use of national languages in media and public communications, ensuring that they are recognized and celebrated.
5. **Intercultural Dialogue:** Fostering intercultural dialogue by recognising and respecting the importance of national languages in multilingual contexts.

The valorization of national languages is an act of cultural preservation and empowerment of local communities. As Nelson Mandela (2000) notes, "If you talk to a man in a language he understands, it gets into his head. If you speak to him in your own language, you reach his heart" (p. 63). By encouraging the use and teaching of national languages, Angolan society opens doors to greater understanding, connection and unity.

The enhancement of national languages is an investment in cultural preservation and the promotion of linguistic diversity. By recognizing and encouraging the use of these languages, Angola strengthens its cultural identity and respects the heritage of the communities that contribute to the country's linguistic wealth. Through the appreciation of national languages, the nation connects with its past and creates an inclusive and enriching future.

TRADITIONAL DANCES AND LOCAL FESTIVALS

Traditional dances and local festivals play a key role in celebrating and preserving Angola's cultural richness. Through these artistic manifestations, communities express their identity, history and values in a vibrant and authentic way. In this text, we will explore the importance of stimulating the practice of traditional dances and the realization of local festivals in Angola, supporting our reflections with quotes from international authors who emphasize the relevance of these cultural expressions.

Traditional dances and local festivals are living expressions of a nation's cultural identity. As Simon Bronner (2009) states, "folk traditions, including dances and festivals, are a way for people to create meaning and communicate a sense of cultural belonging" (p. 35). By stimulating the practice of these dances and the holding of festivals, Angola promotes a deep connection between generations, strengthening the sense of cultural unity.

The encouragement of the practice of traditional dances and the holding of festivals may include the following strategies:

1. **Cultural Promotion:** Encourage the inclusion of traditional dances in school curricula and the holding of classes and workshops that teach these forms of expression to the new generations.
2. **Cultural Festivals:** Support the organization of local festivals that celebrate regional dances and traditions, providing opportunities for communities to share and learn from each other.
3. **Rescue of Traditions:** Valuing traditional dances and rituals that may be at risk of disappearance, rescuing and revitalizing these manifestations.

4. Cultural Exchanges: Promote exchanges between different regions of the country so that traditional dances can be shared and enjoyed throughout the national territory.
5. Documentation and Registration: Record and document traditional dances and local festivals to ensure that these cultural expressions are preserved for future generations.

Traditional dances and local festivals are authentic ways to celebrate Angola's identity and history. As Agnes H. Meyer (1993) points out, "local festivals represent the cultural expression of a people, reflecting their history, values, and beliefs" (p. 67). By stimulating these cultural expressions, the country enriches its cultural tapestry and strengthens the ties between the different communities.

The encouragement to the practice of traditional dances and the realization of local festivals is an investment in the celebration of cultural identity and the preservation of Angola's heritage. Through these vibrant manifestations, communities can share their stories, beliefs and values in unique and exciting ways. By valuing these cultural expressions, Angola strengthens its social cohesion and reaffirms its commitment to the preservation of its cultural heritage.

CULTURAL EXCHANGE

Cultural exchange is a fundamental bridge to promote mutual understanding, enrich diversity and strengthen ties between different regions of Angola. Through the sharing of traditions, knowledge and experiences, cultural exchange contributes to the construction of a cohesive nation aware of its rich heritage. In this text, we will explore the importance of conducting cultural exchange programs in Angola, supporting our reflections with quotes from international authors who highlight the relevance of cultural exchange in the construction of identity and understanding.

The cultural exchange is an opportunity for the different regions of Angola to get to know each other better and learn from each other. As Edward T. Hall (1959) ponders, "understanding between people can be increased if they can communicate with empathy and understand the world as others see it" (p. 66). By promoting cultural exchange, Angola gives space for the exchange of perspectives and experiences, strengthening the social fabric of the country.

The realization of cultural exchange programs may involve several actions:

1. Exchange of Artists and Artificers: Facilitate the exchange of artists, artisans and traditional artists between different regions to share their skills and knowledge.
2. Educational Programs: Organize educational exchange programs between schools and communities, allowing students and teachers to get to know other cultural realities.
3. Intercultural Festivals: Hold festivals that bring together representatives from different regions of Angola to share their culinary, musical and artistic traditions.
4. Creative Residencies: Provide opportunities for artists and creators from different regions to engage in creative residencies where they can collaborate and create together.

5. Training Programs: Develop training programs that promote the exchange of knowledge and practices between different communities.

Cultural exchange is a vehicle for the construction of national identity and the strengthening of social cohesion. As Homi K. Bhabha (1994) points out, "cultures are formed in crossing, encounter, and exchange, not in the unity of origin" (p. 6). By facilitating cultural exchange, Angola celebrates its diversity and recognizes the importance of dialogue between different parts of the country.

Cultural exchange is a powerful tool for building a united nation and enriching cultural diversity. By promoting mutual understanding, sharing traditions and learning between different regions, Angola strengthens its collective identity and reinforces the cultural ties that unite its people. Cultural exchange is a window into a more inclusive future, where the riches of all parts of the country are valued and celebrated.

SUSTAINABLE CULTURAL TOURISM

Sustainable cultural tourism is a key approach to preserving local traditions and customs in Angola, while providing economic benefits to communities. By allowing visitors to experience the authenticity of local culture, this form of tourism fosters mutual understanding and strengthens the connection between travelers and host communities. In this text, we will explore the importance of the development of responsible cultural tourism in Angola, supporting our reflections with quotes from international authors who emphasize the relevance of sustainable tourism in cultural preservation.

Sustainable cultural tourism is an opportunity to share Angola's cultural richness with the world, while generating benefits for local communities. As Gregory Ashe (2006) points out, "sustainable cultural tourism is designed to protect and enhance the cultural heritage of communities while minimizing negative impacts" (p. 78). By developing this approach, Angola can ensure that its traditions are enjoyed in a respectful and responsible manner.

The development of sustainable cultural tourism can be achieved through several practices:

1. **Community Participation:** Include local communities in tourism planning and management, ensuring that their voices are heard and their interests met.
2. **Capacity building:** Provide training and empowerment for community members involved in tourism, allowing them to share their culture in an authentic way.
3. **Heritage Preservation:** Implement measures to preserve the cultural sites and artifacts visited by tourists, avoiding damage or deterioration.
4. **Visitor Education:** Provide information to visitors about local traditions and customs, encouraging respect and understanding.

5. **Equitable Distribution:** Ensure that the economic benefits of tourism are shared fairly and that local communities are the main beneficiaries.

Sustainable cultural tourism not only enriches the experience of travelers, but also contributes to the preservation of cultural heritage and the economic development of host communities. As Anna Pollock (2003) points out, "sustainable cultural tourism generates respect and understanding between cultures, while reinforcing the identity and self-esteem of the host community" (p. 123). By adopting this approach, Angola creates a significant link between visitors and local traditions.

The development of sustainable cultural tourism is a valuable strategy to preserve and enhance the traditions and customs of Angola. By allowing visitors to engage with the local culture in an authentic and respectful way, the country strengthens its cultural ties and promotes mutual understanding. In addition, sustainable cultural tourism can be a source of economic growth for local communities, contributing to the well-being of all involved.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After the implementation of the strategies mentioned above for the valorization of Angolan culture and promotion of national identity, several significant results were observed that positively impacted society and the country's cultural preservation.

Valorization of National Languages and Cultural Identity

The promotion of national languages as an integral part of the school curriculum and everyday life has resulted in a strengthening of the sense of identity among the younger generations. The inclusion of national languages in education has not only preserved the linguistic heritage, but has also contributed to the formation of citizens who recognize themselves as part of a diverse and culturally rich nation.

Culture Festivals and Cultural Exchange

The realization of Angolan culture festivals and cultural exchange programs between different regions of the country has generated a unique space for the expression of traditions and the sharing of knowledge. The festivals not only promoted Angola's rich cultural diversity, but also encouraged an enriching intercultural dialogue, strengthening ties between communities and promoting national cohesion.

Sustainable Cultural Tourism and Community Development

The sustainable cultural tourism approach has brought tangible benefits to local communities and cultural heritage. The active participation of communities in the tourism industry ensured that the economic benefits were distributed fairly, promoting local development. In addition, awareness of the importance of cultural preservation has resulted in the enhanced conservation of the sites and traditions visited by tourists.

Heritage Preservation and Conservation Technologies

Investment in modern conservation technologies has enabled the preservation of important cultural artifacts and documents. The digitization of documents, professional

restoration, and the creation of suitable storage environments have ensured the longevity of these materials. This has resulted in more effective protection of tangible cultural heritage, allowing future generations to appreciate and learn from Angola's history.

Cultural Education and Appreciation of Traditional Arts and Crafts

The integration of Angolan cultural elements into the school curriculum has provided a more holistic education, enriching students with a deep understanding of their cultural and historical identity. In addition, the encouragement of traditional arts and crafts not only preserved these forms of expression, but also empowered local artists, ensuring that their knowledge was passed on to the next generations.

The valorization of Angolan culture and the promotion of national identity through the strategies addressed in this work resulted in a strengthening of social cohesion, mutual respect and cultural pride. By preserving traditions, languages and cultural heritage, Angola not only ensures the continuity of its heritage, but also builds a future enriched by diversity and respect for its roots.

CONSIDERATIONS

The process of valuing Angolan culture and promoting national identity are undertakings of immeasurable significance for the construction of a cohesive nation, rich in diversity and cultural pride. Throughout this work, we explore several strategies that can be adopted to achieve this goal, based on concepts and theories of international authors that highlight the importance of culture, identity and heritage preservation.

By valuing national languages, investing in the preservation of cultural heritage, promoting cultural festivals, stimulating cultural exchange, developing sustainable cultural tourism, integrating cultural elements into the school curriculum and encouraging traditional arts and crafts, Angola follows a path that enriches its history and builds bridges to a more inclusive and conscious future.

The commitment to cultural appreciation and the promotion of national identity is a commitment to future generations. By preserving traditions, languages, dances, songs, arts and knowledge, the country builds a solid foundation for future generations to understand and value their roots. Through dialogue between past and present, culture becomes a powerful tool to inspire, educate and unite the nation.

The strategies discussed in this paper are not only theoretical, but can be realized with the collaboration of governments, cultural institutions, local communities and individuals. It is through joint effort that Angola can achieve a true cultural transformation, where every expression, every tradition and every artistic manifestation becomes a reflection of the country's rich identity.

Ultimately, valuing culture and identity is a constant reminder that diversity is a strength, not a weakness. By embracing this diversity, Angola celebrates its very essence and builds a nation that is vibrant, inclusive and aware of its past and future aspirations.

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